

EVIDENCE-BASED GUIDELINES FOR LACERATION REPAIR IN URGENT CARE SETTING

Hengky Lim, DNP, NP-C | Southern California CSU DNP Consortium | School of Nursing

Introduction

- Lacerations constitute a significant amount of trauma-related visits and are responsible for 8% of the 95 million visits to emergency departments in the United States every year.
- Urgent care (UC) is the provision of immediate medical service focused on the delivery of ambulatory care for non-life threatening medical conditions including most non-complicated lacerations.
- Laceration repairs account for 4.2 million patient visits to urgent care centers annually.

Problem Statement

- Lack of clinical practice guidelines for laceration repair in urgent care center.
- Immediate effects: unnecessary use of antibiotic prophylaxis, infections, hemorrhage, pain, edema, dehiscence.
- Long term effects: hypertrophic scars, hyper/hypopigmentation, nerve damage, poor cosmetic alignment.
- Financial, psychosocial, and legal implications

Goals

DEVELOP	REDUCE	IMPROVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guideline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infection rate Unnecessary antibiotic prophylaxis Healthcare costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Health outcomes Clinicians' consistency

Methodology

- PDSA model used as theoretical framework
- Review of literature on scholarly studies
- Table of Evidence for coordination and synthesis of evidence
- JHNEBP evidence appraisal instruments
- Demographic, wound characteristics and expert evaluation tools
- Expert panel consultations
- Develop and refine EB CPG

Clinical Practice Guidelines

Conceptual Framework

Implications

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Healthcare costs ↓ Medications ↓ Infection rates ↓ Follow up ↓ Complications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↓ Liability ↑ Safety Outdated CPG Utilized by attorneys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ↑ Prognosis ↑ Healing process ↑ Cosmetic outcomes ↓ Wound infections
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Conclusion

- Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines are very powerful educational tools for clinicians in guiding their clinical practice
- The results of using EB CPG are improved quality of care and health care expenditures.
- The literature and experts in guidelines recommend clinicians to utilize the EB CPG as a guide for care in their clinical practice.
- EB CPG should never replace clinical judgment considering differences in physical, psychosocial, and comorbidities of every individual patient.
- The majority of patients seen for non-complicated laceration repairs in a UC are suitable and can be treated following this EB CPG.

Contact

extrajoss@csu.fullerton.edu

Results

Laceration Closure Time

- Approximate a laceration within the first 12 hours.
- A laceration closure time of < 6 hours is significantly associated with a lower infection rate.
- Wound age was not a single significant indicator of infection risk in simple laceration repair.

Antibacterial Prophylaxis

- Current evidence does not support the use of antibiotic prophylaxis in simple laceration repair of wounds less than 12 hours old with appropriate wound cleaning and closure.
- Clinical judgment in prescribing antibiotics prophylaxis should be based on a case by case basis considering individual circumstances. Wound characteristics, location and degree of contamination are important factors to consider when making a decision to put a patient on antibiotic prophylaxis.

Wound Locations

- Wound infection is less likely to occur on the neck, face, and scalp.
- Wound infections are more likely to occur on extremities, especially lower extremities.

Characteristics

- The clinician should consider the role of wound characteristics as a factor in infection rates. Lacerations more than 5 cm or longer that are deeper, wider, jagged and/or have noticeable debris may develop wound infection.

Irrigation Solutions

- Infection rates are not affected by types of solution, such as NS, tap water, and antiseptic solutions.
- Antiseptic solutions for wound irrigation may be harmful to healthy tissue and delay wound healing.

Irrigation Pressure

- Optimal volume of irrigation is between 50 and 100 mL per cm of wound length.
- Constant flow with pressure of 8 to 12 psi on wound surface.
- Extremely high pressure can cause tissue damage & increase infection risk.

Debridement

- Ischemic or gangrenous wounds should be excised and approximated immediately if there is no intrinsic, extrinsic, or mechanical damage requiring surgical intervention or healing by secondary intention.

Irrigation versus No Irrigation

- The clinician should properly clean the wound prior to closure to prevent wound infection.
- There is no difference in post laceration repair outcomes with or without irrigation on non-contaminated highly vascular area, such as neck, face and/or scalp.
- Children will have the same, if not better, outcomes post laceration repair even if their lacerations are less likely to be cleaned prior to closure.